

Microwave sensor to determine fruit quality

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In this work, long microwaves are used to identify some quality levels of various fruits, which can be purchased in popular markets and supermarkets in Medellín, Colombia. The electromagnetic waves operate in a range of 300 to 600 MHz, ranging from 100 to 50 cm in air. When generated by the equipment, these waves travel to the permittivity sensor connected to the equipment and are radiated by the sensor to propagate through the selected fruits, the combination of sensor and fruit determines both the response frequency and its intensity. Thus, according to the response obtained by the sensor, this technique allows for determining some specific characteristics of the fruit, such as the amount of juice concerning the others, the level of ripeness, or whether its state is still suitable for human consumption. This identification method offers the advantage of being non-invasive, so the fruit does not need to be subjected to a chemical to be analyzed, altering its flavor or consistency, nor is it damaged or needs to be discarded after examination. In addition, the equipment used for the study is inexpensive and portable, therefore, the analysis can be performed in the field, in storage warehouses, or on commercial shelves, since it is only necessary to place the sensor on the fruit or vice versa, activate the generation of electromagnetic waves in the equipment and wait three seconds to obtain the response of the quality level analysis.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In a world where we are surrounded by diverse and different products and bombarded all the time with advertising in various media, platforms, advertisements, and flyers, to acquire more products; in reality, few products are considered indispensable for human beings, such as air, water, food, a place to rest and security. To be considered as having a better standard of living, certain basic amenities and services can be included. While it is true that we usually want to have more amenities and products available at our fingertips or to own them permanently, the variety of amenities and products available to different people is wide.

However, regardless of region, country, economic stratum, age, gender, race, or nationality, what a person seeks and requires every day is a place to rest, water, and food. For this reason, the global food industry is one of the most important not only for the need for food but also for economic matters. For example, by 2024, Worldmetrics has estimated that the revenue of the food industry will be \$10.4 trillion [1]. Recently, due to the serious health problems of current generations, as well as the enormous ecological damage caused by certain human activities and industrial sectors, there has been a significant growth in the number of people who not only want to eat healthily, but also want the food they consume to be produced in an environmentally responsible way, does not cause harm to wildlife, or require excessive water consumption. This trend is so strong that it is estimated that by 2027 the global organic food market will grow to \$679.8 billion [1].

Although the global trend indicates that more and more people will seek to consume foods that are considered healthy and sustainable, grouped in a category known as organic food, which includes the great diversity of fruits and vegetables, how can we know before consuming them that the food has an acceptable level of quality? For this reason, most companies involved in the industrial production of food try to keep rigorous control over the conditions in which the food is planted, grown, cultivated, packaged, stored, and distributed. This, of course, includes the amount of water with which the crops are irrigated, the growing time required for each specific fruit and vegetable, and the types and amounts of nutrients, fertilizers, and pesticides that are added to each of the crops, which is not only done to ensure that the final product obtained possesses the ideal characteristics sought but also serves to minimize production costs, as well as the amount of materials used, to be more environmentally responsible [2-3].

Despite these rigorous controls and the multiple similarities that the final products obtained may have, the foods will have certain differences not only in their appearance but also in their composition. This implies, for example, that even a fruit from the same tree may have a higher amount of juice than another fruit that is practically identical. So, how could we determine which particular fruit within a group of fruits of the same type has a higher amount of juice? Which one has the lowest amount of juice? How many of them meet the minimum required amount?

Being able to answer these non-trivial questions has become more and more relevant because consumers are looking for this type of product considering the best characteristics, even though this represents a higher cost. Therefore, being able to separate their final product into different quality levels could bring economic benefits for food industries if the total economic cost of performing this type of separation is not too high.

Although it cannot be generalized that, for all types of fruit, among the great diversity that exists, having a greater amount of juice also implies that it is a more palatable fruit, this may only be true for some fruits, especially if a certain degree of sweetness is added. For example, if we refer in particular to mandarins, they are usually preferred for their juiciness and sweetness, which is why, if different quality levels were classified, the specific purpose that could be attributed to each one for sale according to its quality level could be as described below:

- Optimum. With a great amount of juice and sweetness, intended for sale in bulk as a gourmet product.
- High. With a good amount of juice and sweetness, intended for sale in bulk as a quality product or for the production of quality juices.

- Medium. With an acceptable amount of juice or sweetness, intended for sale in bulk as a good product or the production of juices.
- Low. Low in juice and sweetness, intended for sale as fruit nectar.

Although there are experts in the harvesting of fruits and vegetables who can determine the quality of each one of them by simple visual and tactile inspection, the trend in this specific area of work, as well as in other areas, is an increase in the difficulty of finding qualified people who want to work in this sector. One of the unattended problems that can cause national and even global crises is the lack of workers in the field, at least in small-scale production, that is, independent producers who are not backed by large corporations. An ignored reality is that fieldwork is a difficult and low-paying occupation. This, added to other problems such as water scarcity and, a decrease in the amount of rainfall, among other things, has led to a decrease in the number of people engaged in agricultural activity in entire regions of several continents [4]. For this reason, many small farmers are abandoning their crops and looking for other sources of income, or migrating to the cities, or even to other countries.

Recently, small-scale production has been seriously affected, especially in countries with populist governments where they have withdrawn support and subsidies to the countryside, and at the same time they tend to hand out handouts, this added to the restriction of transgenic seeds and certain herbicides gives the small producer even more disadvantage compared to multinationals or producers in other countries where these impediments do not exist. For this reason, for many small farmers, it has become more profitable to receive government handouts, or to emigrate in masse, than to engage in a difficult and undervalued activity such as agriculture [5-6].

In practically all countries, small farmers have survived on government subsidies, because without these subsidies it is not profitable for them to engage in these activities. Paradoxically, it is the contributions of these small producers that prevent food shortages and, as a consequence, a massive increase in the prices of these products, since this type of production is mostly dedicated to self-consumption or local or regional consumption. Governments used to understand this well, since it was profitable for a country to provide massive subsidies to small producers, compared to having to face product shortages with the respective consequences that such insufficiency would have on the countries [7].

While for small producers, with each passing year, their situation seems to worsen, the outlook for multinational food producers is very different, it seems that, as the years go by, food production becomes an increasingly lucrative business [1]. Many agree that to make food production a productive business, it is necessary to industrialize, that is, to have enough machinery to facilitate the work, to reduce the time and effort required in production, as well as to have better control of the production processes [8]. Considering the above, this article presents a permittivity sensor operating in the microwave range, which is used to identify quality levels in fruits such as avocado, passion fruit, tangerine, mango, orange, papaya, and tree tomato. The following questions about the use of a permittivity sensor to analyze various fruits are intended to be answered.

1. Is it possible to classify fruit quality?
2. Is it possible to determine the amount of juice in some types of fruit?
3. Would it be possible to estimate the level of ripeness of some types of fruit even before they are harvested?
4. Would the operating range be the same for all fruits?

The results obtained from this research will help us discern if it is possible to have a fully automated process that analyzes a variety of fruits to determine their quality.

2. METHOD

This research was carried out using the following in the results obtained by experimental measurements: statistical analysis, comparison of results, observation of maximum and minimum values, and relation in

the widths of the resonances. All this is based on the already established and accepted theory in electromagnetism and electromagnetic properties of matter.

Every material, including vacuum, has an electrical permittivity and magnetic permeability unique to that particular material, regardless of the state of aggregation of the material, i.e., whether it is in its solid, liquid, or gaseous state. Most materials share the same magnetic permeability value, this has to do with the fact that the materials will not have an internal arrangement in the dipoles of their magnetic charges when an external magnetic field is applied to them. Only ferromagnetic materials have a relative permeability greater than one, that is, only those materials have a magnetic permeability greater than that of a vacuum. Relative permittivity will be discussed in more detail later and this explanation can be extended to relative permeability.

Although the permittivity values may change in the same material due to factors to which the material is exposed such as temperature, pressure, and humidity of the environment, the material under the same conditions maintains its permittivity values, which is why we consider them unique and exclusive to the material. In addition, the permittivity values of the material are intimately linked to its molecular structure; if this structure changes, so will its permittivity values. Thus, a molecular structure can change by temperature as the molecules expand or contract, by external pressure as the molecules join or separate, by introducing an external agent and combining with the molecules of the material to form either a different molecular structure or by changing the size of that structure.

How large the change is depends directly on how much the original molecular structure is affected, and this in turn depends on how large the change in temperature, pressure, or amount of external agent introduced. If these variations are small, the changes in permittivity values will be small and may be imperceptible if the technique used to monitor the permittivity is not sufficiently sensitive. Now, although the molecular structure is what determines the permittivity values, the dielectric properties of a material can be determined macroscopically, and with this determination, it is possible to know how the material will interact with external electromagnetic energy applied to it [9].

But what are dielectric properties? In order not to delve into the molecular structures of materials and to present a more complex study, it is much more practical to treat the material as a single object, i.e. not that it is composed of small parts of perhaps different molecules, but as a single material of much larger size than the molecules and to study it from a macroscopic perspective. The term electrical permittivity is directly related to the ability of a material to allow the formation of electric fields within it, and in turn, the propagation of those electric fields through it. Unlike how they react with magnetic permeability, virtually all materials found in nature have a permittivity greater than that of a vacuum (excluding conductive metals and metamaterials).

When an external electric field is applied to the material, this field exerts a force on each electric charge dipole inside the material and this force orients the positive charges in one direction and the negative charges in the opposite direction. This orientation of charges allows the material to polarize, i.e., in one direction it has a positive charge and in the opposite direction it has a negative charge. In turn, this polarization generates another electric field inside the material, which is different from the external field that was applied to it, these fields unite resulting in an apparent electric field larger than the one that was originally applied [10]. Thus, the variation capacity of this electric field resulting from the union of both fields can be directly related to the electrical permittivity, where the materials that usually have larger changes are dielectric, therefore, the term dielectric permittivity of the material is often used to refer to how large this variation could be.

Although permittivity indicates to what degree the resulting electric field will be in a material to which an external electric field is applied, this behavior of the material is not the only thing that can be related to permittivity. For example, an electrical signal that is applied to one end of the material to propagate through it and leave it at the other end will surely have a different amplitude from the initial one, and if that same signal is applied to a different material, the amplitude will not only be different from the one that was applied, but it will also be different from the one that left the other material. So, the permittivity of a material

tells us how much a signal wave propagating through that material will be attenuated, what the velocity of that propagating wave will be, what the length of that wave oscillation within the material will be, as well as the refractive index of that material [11].

The Greek letter ϵ (epsilon) is used as a symbol to express permittivity which has units of F/m (Farad/meter). It is much more practical to normalize the permittivity of materials using the vacuum permittivity which is the following value $\epsilon_0 = 8.8542 \times 10^{-12}$ F/m, this not only makes it dimensionless but indicates directly how large the permittivity of that material compared to the vacuum permittivity. This value is called relative permittivity and is expressed as ϵ_r . The relative permittivity is a complex variable, which can be described in equation (1).

$$\epsilon_r = \epsilon' - j\epsilon'' = \epsilon'(1 - j \tan \delta) \quad (1)$$

Where ϵ is the value of the imaginary part of the permittivity, ϵ' is the value of the real part of the permittivity, so $\delta = \epsilon''/\epsilon'$ is called loss tangent and represents the ratio between the imaginary part and the real part of the relative permittivity. Similarly, the value of ϵ'' of a material indicates the degree of attenuation that a wave propagating through that material will have and has a minimum value at zero which is only the case for a lossless medium. The higher the value of ϵ'' , the more losses a wave propagating through the material will have.

It should be noted that, despite not varying the temperature, pressure, or external humidity, the permittivity value of a material is different for signals with different frequencies. This has to do with the size of the signal wave, for example, if you have a cobblestone street, a monster truck, a tractor, or a dump truck would hardly have problems in circulating on that street. However, a small car or bicycle would have a very bumpy ride, and for someone on roller skates, it would probably be impossible to navigate. Something similar happens with the signals that travel through a material, for low-frequency signals (large wavelengths) the material seems to be uniform, without apparent deformations or irregularities, as the frequency of the signal increases (and the wavelength becomes smaller) the signal begins to feel anomalies in the material, the path becomes more complicated, and as the frequency increases, the wave will seem that the material is much less uniform.

The real part of the permittivity ϵ' is used to calculate the velocity of the signal traveling inside the material, the wavelength that signal has inside the material, the impedance that the signal encounters in the material, and the refractive index of the material. As mentioned above, for any natural material, the permittivity value will be larger than that of the vacuum, so the relative permittivity will always be greater than 1. For example, air has a relative permittivity of about 1.0006. The value of the relative permittivity in materials depends on many factors such as density, humidity in the medium, temperature, the different elements of the periodic table that make up the material, and the microstructure or molecular composition of the material. Not forgetting that it also depends on the frequency of the signal applied to the material and that the value of the real part of the relative permittivity decreases as the frequency increases.

The following equations show the relationship of the signal velocity c within a material, the signal wavelength within the material λ , and the material refractive index n , as a function of the value of the real part of the relative permittivity ϵ_r for non-magnetic materials, i.e., where the permeability of the material is the same as that of the vacuum (equations (2), (3), (4)).

$$c = \frac{c_0}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r}} \quad (2)$$

$$\lambda = \frac{\lambda_0}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r}} \quad (3)$$

$$n = \sqrt{\epsilon_r} \quad (4)$$

Where c_0 is the speed of light or electromagnetic wave in vacuum 3×10^8 m/s, λ_0 is the length of the electromagnetic wave in vacuum defined in equation (5) which shows the relationship between the velocity of the wave and its frequency f .

$$\lambda_0 = \frac{c_0}{f} \quad (5)$$

Recently, the dielectric properties of materials have been of increasing interest, particularly in the areas of agriculture, industry, and medicine because of the information that can be obtained from them indirectly. Such information includes, but is not limited to: the concentration level of the material, presence of contaminants, density, moisture absorbed by the material, and authenticity [12-14]. Thus, there are two methods for measuring the dielectric properties of a material: resonant and non-resonant. Both methods have their advantages and disadvantages, for example, resonant methods are much more sensitive and accurate, but their frequency operating range is small or very limited, and they are only preferred for low-loss materials. On the other hand, the resonant method can be either a dielectric resonator or a perturbation.

In this work, we use a resonant method based on the perturbation-resonance theory, where both the resonance quality factor and its frequency value change when a sample is introduced into the resonator. Also, the resonant frequency of a resonator depends on the following characteristics: the physical dimensions of the resonator, the type of resonator it is, the material from which it is made, and the material in which it is immersed. In addition, the quality factor of a resonator depends on some properties such as the material from which the resonator is made, the material in which it is immersed, and the design of the resonator [15].

Once the resonator is designed and manufactured, the material to be characterized can only become part of the resonator, or as in the method we use in this work, part of the medium in which the resonator is immersed. When there is no material to characterize or sample on the resonator, the material in which the resonator is immersed is only air. Thus, when a sample is placed on top of the resonator, the material in which the resonator is immersed will be both the sample and air in the spaces not occupied by the sample. Figure 1 shows the moment of a measurement where a resonance curve is displayed on the laptop screen.

Figure 1. Dielectric Permittivity Measurement

In total, the components required for a measurement are:

- A permittivity sensor designed with microwave technology techniques with 50 ohms input resistance and an SMA connector soldered to its power terminal, where the sensor is based on a composite metamaterial resonator. In addition, the sensor is fabricated on a commercial phenolic plate which is made with a double-sided FR4 substrate of $\epsilon_r = 4.4$, $\tan \delta = 0.02$, the substrate thickness is 16 mm and the thickness of both copper faces is 35 μm . The sensor size is 50 mm x 32 mm, the size of the outer radius of the circular resonator is 31 mm, and the width of the resonator line is 2 mm. Similarly, the coupling between the feed and the resonator is capacitive. More information on the operation of a composite metamaterial resonator can be found in [16].
- One fruit or sample to be measured and characterized. All tests were carried out at room temperature, which was between 23 and 29 degrees Celsius, where the fruit was not refrigerated to avoid condensation on the fruit.
- An AURSINC brand Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) Nano, which has an operating frequency of 50 kHz to 4 GHz and a resolution of 10 kHz. The Nano VNA can be used without the need for a computer with 501 different frequency points in 1.3 seconds.

- An Acer Nitro 5 laptop. However, any current laptop would work without problems since the functional requirements of the Nano VNA are minimal. Using a laptop offers the advantage of having 1031 points instead of 501, as well as displaying on a larger screen, controlling the Nano VNA from the computer, and saving measured data directly to the computer.
- A 50-ohm high-frequency coaxial cable to connect the Nano VNA port to the SMA connector of the sensor.
- A USB cable to connect the computer to the Nano VNA.
- NanoVNA-Saver software to control the VNA from the PC and save measurements.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section shows the experimental results obtained by using the permittivity sensor in the microwave range, to obtain the response to the perturbation-resonance technique that is generated when we use the following fruits as a perturbation medium: avocado, passion fruit, tangerine, mango, orange, papaya, and tree tomato. All the fruits were obtained from supermarkets, chosen the day they were put on the shelf so that they were as fresh as possible, the fruits were not refrigerated and were kept in the shade at room temperature, all this was done in the city of Medellin, so the ambient temperature was higher than 23°C, being between 23 and 29°C.

3.1 Avocado

The presentation of the different fruits is in alphabetical order, the first fruit to be presented is the avocado in its variety Lorena or Papelillo. This avocado variety was chosen because it is the most popular in the region. Figure 2 shows the frequency response of a Lorena avocado, where it can be seen that from the first to the fifth day the tendency of the frequency value is decreasing, after that the tendency changes and becomes random.

The avocado was picked when it was not ripe for consumption, even though it was too hard, by day 3 the avocado could already be consumed. On day 4 the avocado was already soft, on day 5 it began to change color, turning dark spots and from day 7 the dark color overcame the green. In the first five days, there is a well-defined tendency despite having made random measurements, that is, not always measuring the same part of the avocado. This is because internally the structure of the avocado is uniform and does not have an anisotropy or orientation as is the case with other types of fruit.

Figure 2. Resonance frequency values generated by a Papelillo avocado as a function of time in days

3.2 Granadilla

The next fruit was the passion fruit. Figures 3 and 4 show the results obtained in the value of the resonance frequency and the value of the return loss, in both cases as a function of time in days. The shape and consistency of the passion fruit make it difficult to analyze by this means. The figures show a comparison of the results obtained for two different fruits; the fruits were chosen in such a way that, despite being similar in size, their weight was different.

Figure 3. Values of resonance frequencies generated by some grenadillas as a function of time in days

Figure 4. Return loss values generated by some grenadillas as a function of time in days

The first point to highlight from the experimental results is that the resonance frequency value is much higher compared to the paper avocado and in general for the different fruits, being this resonance frequency value 100 MHz above the average for most of the fruits (20% above the average). Additionally, the granadilla is a pomegranate-like fruit, which has a very brittle semi-hard shell, then a very low-density layer that protects the fruit, while the fruit is mostly seed (as in the pomegranate) with some pulp. This makes the density of the passion fruit low and the protective layer closer in consistency to air than to fruit pulp. Therefore, this low density due to the protective layer and the fact that it is mostly seed inside, generates a high resonance frequency value.

Figure 4 shows the return loss values, these values are slightly above the expected average, which indicates that, despite its low density, it does have a detectable amount of water inside. Although the responses obtained do show an appreciable difference for the two samples, we consider that this type of fruit would be difficult to classify using microwaves, because two fruits with evidently very different densities were chosen.

3.3 Mandarin

The third fruit is the mandarin in its imported variety. In the case of the mandarin as in other fruits, its composition is anisotropic, and being formed internally by segments, it gives the mandarin a different composition in its parallel direction from the one it has in its meridian direction. Thus, the mandarins were placed on the sensor in such a way that the meridian direction coincided with the vertical. From this perspective, the amount of water (juice) detected is expected to be less than if it were detected from the parallel direction. Also, since the fibers that make up the non-bunch part are of low density, this would make the results more random. This direction was chosen to test the robustness of the technique on a fruit from which juice is usually obtained.

Figure 5 shows the results obtained for two dry mandarins, or mandarins with low juice quantity. It should be noted that the tests were done for six mandarins and at the end, their juice quantity levels were classified

by opening them and directly testing the amount of juice in them with a destructive test. The mandarins were not refrigerated and were kept for 9 days at room temperature. Thus, Figure 5 shows that in the last 3 days, both curves reveal high values of resonance frequency and that this jump was from the fifth day for one curve and the seventh day for the other curve.

Figure 5. Values of resonance frequencies generated by mandarins as a function of time in days

In addition, the blue curve shows that it had its lowest values between the second and fourth day, while the red curve shows that the resonance values oscillated between 513 MHz and 540 MHz between day one and day five. This oscillation is normal and to be expected when measurements are made randomly at the exact location of the sample that will be over the center point of the sensor. The reason why it is done randomly despite knowing that these oscillations will exist is because the purpose of this work is to see if it is feasible to automate a fruit characterization system with a microwave sensor.

Figure 6 shows the responses generated by the mandarins with the highest amount of juice. Although the random oscillatory behavior is indeed repeated, it can also be appreciated that both curves present three areas with well-defined behaviors. The first one, from the first day to the fourth day, shows average oscillating values of the resonance frequencies. The second area shows a decrease in the resonance frequency values between days five and six, which represents an area of minimum values. The third and last area between days seven and nine shows a sudden increase in frequency values to reach the maximum of each curve, after which the oscillatory behavior continues. Figure 5 also shows this behavior in mandarins, which have a period of medium frequencies, with the time they finish ripening to reach their ideal point where they will have the maximum possible amount of juice, to later pass to the period where their best stage is left behind and consequently, they will have the least amount of juice possible.

Figure 6. Values of resonance frequencies generated by mandarins as a function of time in days

The results obtained show that regardless of whether this type of fruit has a low or high amount of juice, its behavior concerning time will be similar. That is to say, for some time after being cut it will have a medium amount of juice, after that it will reach its maximum level and then pass to the period where it will begin to dry out and lose moisture.

Certainly, the minimum level will depend on how mature it was at the time of cutting, for example, Figure 5 shows a minimum between days three and five, while in Figure 6 the minimums are between days five and

six. The minimum values for Figure 5 are below 480 MHz for the blue curve and 520 MHz for the red curve, while the maximums are above 550 MHz for the blue curve and 570 MHz for the red curve. In contrast, for Figure 6 the minima are below 450 MHz and the maxima are above 510 MHz, which are comparable to the minimum values of the low juice mandarins with an easily identifiable difference.

3.4 Handle

Now it is the turn of the Tommy variety of mango. This type of mango has peculiarities that make it different from the other types of fruit presented here. One of them is that it is usually consumed green and many prefer it in that condition. The reason why it is consumed green may have to do with the fact that it is a fruit that takes many days to ripen after being cut. So, it is a fruit that can last many days green until it finally begins to change color and consistency starting to take a yellow and reddish hue. Because of the shape of the handle, the only way to position it on the sensor without having to put something to immobilize and hold it is in its horizontal shape. Also, the shape of the handle only allows for two possible options in horizontal placement making the measurements less random than other fruits.

Although in appearance it gives the impression that it does not change over time, in its composition changes do occur as can be seen in Figure 7, which shows a continuous period of decreasing value of the resonance frequency until reaching day three and a half (with a value out of range on day 2), after reaching a local minimum the resulting frequency begins to rise in value until reaching a local maximum on day five and a half. From that day on, and despite the oscillations that are a result of making random measurements, a downward trend can be seen in the resulting values of resonance frequencies. Of the fruits analyzed, mango is the one with the highest resulting frequency variation, starting with 516 MHz in its greenest stage until reaching 349 MHz on the last day, however, this variation is in the longest period.

Figure 7. Resonance frequency values generated by a mango as a function of time in days

3.5 Orange

In fifth place, we have the orange in its juice variety. The orange like other fruits is anisotropic, but as it was with the tangerine, it is much easier to place it on a semi-flat surface with its direction parallel to the horizon, which is why the orange was placed on the sensor in that shape and direction. Figure 8 shows the results obtained by placing a juice orange on the sensor and making measurements of the resulting frequency response. For the first five days, there are no considerable oscillations.

There is a clear downward trend for the resulting resonance frequency values in the first four measurements to reach a minimum frequency value of 406 MHz on day two. This indicates that at that time the orange had the highest amount of juice. Thereafter, the trend is upward until day three and a half where for five measurements the resonance frequency value stays within a short range of values. From day 6 onwards, pronounced oscillations can be seen. Thus, for oranges as for other fruits, the period when it has its best conditions is in the range of five days of purchase. It is important to mention again that this period is without refrigeration, keeping the fruit at room temperature.

Figure 8. Resonance frequency values generated by an orange as a function of time in days

3.6 Papaya

The papaya has the characteristic of having a hollow center and a very thin skin. As with the previous fruits, a papaya of not very mature appearance was chosen, although due to the nature of this fruit, it is not as immature as the avocado or mango. The papaya, being elongated, is also anisotropic, but since it does not have segments or stones like the avocado or mango, this anisotropy is to a lesser extent than other fruits. The variation in the values of the frequencies from the first measurement to its minimum on the third day and a half is also of a wide range. These values range from 445 MHz for the maximum to 310 MHz for the minimum, as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Values of resonance frequencies generated by a papaya as a function of time in days.

Due to the specific conditions of having thin skin, a hollow center, and not being fibrous, papaya also presents a peculiarity when applied to electromagnetic waves in the microwave range. This peculiarity is that it has a semi-continuous degree of transparency during the period that would be considered best for consumption. As can be seen in Figure 10, for the first measurement there is a value of -6 dB for return loss. This value increases in amplitude to almost -16 dB for the second measurement and remains below this value until day four.

We consider it important to emphasize that higher negative amplitudes for the return loss imply that there is better coupling between the sensor and the sample, which in these cases are fruits. That is, more energy passes from the sensor to the fruit. In antennas values below -10 dB are considered acceptable because they indicate that less than 10% of the delivered energy is reflected and that the remaining energy was transferred to the antenna. Therefore, we can conclude that a non-green papaya accepts the transfer of electromagnetic waves in the microwave range.

A 135 MHz variation is impressive for many microwave systems, materials, or devices used at those frequencies, but that this is only in three and a half days is even more unexpected. In a short time, there are huge changes in the chemistry and internal composition of papaya. Beginning with the fourth day there is an increase in the value of the resonance frequency that stays within a range until it begins to fall and oscillate. By those days the papaya was in what many would consider bad shape.

Figure 10. Return loss values generated by a papaya as a function of time in days

3.7 Tree tomato

Last but not least, it is the turn of the tree tomato. The tree tomato is similar in shape and color to the red tomato. This fruit also has an anisotropic structure as it is usually elongated and semi-cylindrical with curvatures at the ends. Due to its shape, it is much easier to place on a semi-flat surface with its meridian direction towards the horizon. The shell of this fruit is thin and its size is small compared to the other fruits analyzed, but it is large enough to be analyzed by this sensor. Figure 11 shows the results after experimental measurements and the respective processing of the data obtained. The graph shows a resonance frequency value of 512 MHz for the first measurement, then a downward trend until reaching the minimum value of 373 MHz on the third day and a half, to then enter the decay stage where oscillatory values begin with considerable changes in the amplitude of the resonance frequency value. The results show that this tree tomato specimen had a life span of where it was in its best conditions to be consumed 4 days.

Figure 11. Resonance frequency values generated by a tree tomato as a function of time in days.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The results obtained show interesting data: most of the fruits analyzed have a period in which they are in the best conditions to be consumed; this period is between three and a half to five days. This is in agreement with the popular belief that fruit is good until five days after being acquired and with the custom of discarding fruits after three days in the privileged sectors.

It appears that the internal changes in the fruit are rapid and immense during the period from the time they are cut to the end of ripening, as the variations in the resonance frequency value are enormous, especially on the first day. It would be interesting to see the change in information on fruit chemistry during this period.

The variation in the resonance frequency value of mango was the largest (167 MHz), however, also the period was the largest for this fruit, this period being almost three times longer than for papaya (135 MHz) and tree tomato (139 MHz).

At least about the fruits analyzed in this work, it seems that it is the peel that influences the length of the period for which the fruit is in its best condition, with thin-skinned fruits having a period of three and a half days, while fruits with thicker peels have a longer period.

According to the results obtained, it would be possible to classify different fruits by their quality level using the microwave sensor used in this study in conjunction with a probabilistic classification criterion established with the values of mean, variance, and standard deviation of a set of samples.

The sensor would allow us to detect with better precision the moment of best condition of the fruit to be consumed, because, in fruits such as avocado, papaya, and tree tomato, the external and visible signs of ripening almost coincide with the period in which the minimum value of the resonance frequency occurs, since the external signs of the beginning of overripening appear one to two days after the minimum detected by the sensor.

Additionally, at least in mandarins and oranges, it is possible to determine which specimens have the highest amount of juice. Likewise, it would be possible to estimate the amount of juice of a specimen if the size of the specimen were added to the data table. This confirms as positive the second unknown initially established in this study.

Although both mandarins and oranges after five days appear to be in good condition to be consumed and unlike other fruits, they do not show obvious signs of being or beginning to be in a state of decomposition. However, the analysis shows that internally there are significant changes in their internal composition, therefore, it would be interesting to analyze chemically what these changes occurred, unfortunately, to make chemical analysis requires destructive tests.

The answer to the third question is that, if it were possible to estimate the ripening level of most types of fruit, since, as the results prove, almost all the fruits analyzed in this study show a well-established behavior in their ripening stage. Subsequently, when the fruit enters the overripe stage, the behavior of the sensor response becomes erratic.

In addition, passion fruit is not a fruit in which it is advisable to perform a microwave analysis due to the structural composition of the fruit, where the pulp is in the center, being mostly seeds and covered by a protective layer of low density and with a large amount of space.

Finally, the operating range needed to analyze this set of fruits was not the same, different fruits cause different operating ranges of the sensor, and some fruits generate a wide range of responses. The total operating range covering the entire response spectrum of this set of fruits and the one that was used in the Nano VNA is between 260 MHz and 660 MHz.

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